

On some functorial extensions of doppelsemigroups

Vasyl Stefanyk Precarpathian National University, Ivano-Frankivsk, Ukraine

A family \mathcal{U} of non-empty subsets of a set S is called an *upfamily* if for each set $U \in \mathcal{U}$ any subset $F \supset U$ belongs to \mathcal{U} . The set $v(S)$ of all upfamilies on S is said as *the upfamily extension* of S . It was shown that any associative binary operation $*$: $S \times S \rightarrow S$ can be extended to an associative binary operation $*$: $v(S) \times v(S) \rightarrow v(S)$. In this case, the Stone-Čech compactification $\beta(S)$ of a semigroup S is a subsemigroup of the semigroup $v(S)$. For $k \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{1\}$, an upfamily $\mathcal{U} \in v(S)$ is *k-linked* if $\bigcap \mathcal{L} \neq \emptyset$ for any subfamily $\mathcal{L} \subset \mathcal{U}$ with $|\mathcal{L}| \leq k$. The extension $N_k(S)$ of S consists of all *k-linked* upfamilies on S . Besides the subsemigroup $N_k(S)$, the semigroup $v(S)$ also contains the subsemigroup $\lambda(S)$ of maximal 2-linked upfamilies on S . The space $\lambda(S)$ is well-known in General and Categorical Topology as the *superextension* of S .

A *doppelsemigroup* is an algebraic structure (D, \dashv, \vdash) consisting of a non-empty set D equipped with two associative binary operations \dashv and \vdash satisfying the axioms $(x \dashv y) \vdash z = x \dashv (y \vdash z)$ and $(x \vdash y) \dashv z = x \vdash (y \dashv z)$. In the talk, we discuss the structure of the doppelsemigroups $(v(D), \dashv, \vdash)$, $(\lambda(D), \dashv, \vdash)$, $(N_k(D), \dashv, \vdash)$, $(\beta(D), \dashv, \vdash)$ on a doppelsemigroup (D, \dashv, \vdash) . In particular, we study right and left zeros and identities, commutativity, the center, ideals of these doppelsemigroup extensions. We introduce the functors v , λ , N_k , β in the category **DSG** whose objects are doppelsemigroups and morphisms are doppelsemigroup homomorphisms, and show that these functors preserve strong doppelsemigroups, doppelsemigroups with left (right) zero, doppelsemigroups with left (right) identity, left (right) zeros doppelsemigroups. Also we prove that the automorphism groups of the aforementioned functorial extensions of a doppelsemigroup (D, \dashv, \vdash) contain a subgroup, isomorphic to the automorphism group of (D, \dashv, \vdash) .

- [1] V.M. Gavrylkiv, D.V. Rendziak, Interassociativity and three-element doppelsemigroups, *Algebra Discrete Math.* **28**(2) (2019), 224-247.
- [2] V.M. Gavrylkiv, On the upfamily extension of a doppelsemigroup, *Mat. Stud.* **61**(2) (2024), 123-135.
- [3] V.M. Gavrylkiv, Superextensions of doppelsemigroups, *Carpathian Math. Publ.* **17** (2025)
- [4] V.M. Gavrylkiv, Doppelsemigroups of *k-linked* upfamilies, *J. Algebra Appl.* **25** (2026), 2650207.

E-mail: ✉ vgavrylkiv@gmail.com.